

Level of School Implementation on the Key Dimensions of Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan (BE-LCP): A Basis on Designing Policy Brief for Distance Learning

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Abstract: The main objective of the study is to develop what policy brief for distance learning can be proposed in the Division of Calamba City? Adoption of the Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan (BE-LCP) for school year 2020-2021 considering the covid-19 public health emergency states that the key elements of the learning strategies that shall operationalize the BE-LCP are the streamlining of the K to 12 Curriculum into the Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELCs) and allowing of multiple learning delivery modalities such as distance learning on place of face-to-face learning delivery modality. To help learners, parents, and teachers implement these learning delivery modalities, Self-Learning Modules (SLMs) shall be made available in print and offline/online digital format.

Keywords: BE-LCP – Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan, Distance Learning, MELCs – Most Essential Learning Competencies, K to 12 Curriculum, learning delivery modalities, Self – Learning Modules.

1. INTRODUCTION

1. The global outbreak of the highly contagious new COVID-19 virus, continues to pose unprecedented challenges. At this point, the biggest impact of COVID-19 arises from the need to practice stringent social or physical distancing to prevent or mitigate its spread. For the Department of Education (DepEd), this meant the cancellation of classes and other school activities for the remaining weeks of SY 2019-2020, and that for SY 2020-2021, schools must find ways for learning to continue amidst the threat and uncertainties brought about by COVID-19, while ensuring the health, safety, and well-being of all learners, teachers, and personnel of the Department (BE-LCP-Final-24-May-2020)

2. Adoption of various learning delivery options such as but not limited to face-to-face, blended learnings, distance learnings, and homeschooling and other modes of delivery shall be implemented depending on the local COVID Risk Severity Classification and compliance with minimum health standards as mentioned in the Be-LCP has been implemented to ensure continuous delivery of learning and basic education services (www.teacherph.com/depd-basic-education-learning-continuity-plan-be-lcp-for-sy-2020-2021)

3. To prepare our teachers and school leaders for multiple learning delivery modalities, they shall be capacitated to implement the learning delivery system, consistent with DepEd's professional development framework and professional standards, and the transformation of the National Educators Academy of the Philippines (NEAP). They will be introduced to learning delivery modalities that they can readily utilize depending on community context, and be provided with tools and mechanisms to inform their decision-making. To ensure the seamless transition of learning activities into formats appropriate to platforms and learning delivery modalities they will adopt, capacity building will be implemented beginning

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in June until July 2020. Support mechanisms shall also be established to provide teachers and school leaders access to on demand technical and administrative advice and guidance, (Briones, 2020).

She added that the BE-LCP has been designed with a legal framework responsive to the new normal, keeping in mind the constitutional mandate to uphold the right of all citizens to 5 quality education at all times. The Department also reviewed and assessed the programs, projects and activities outlined in the plan and their corresponding budgetary implications. The available program funds are being maximized, reprogrammed, or realigned to the programs, projects, and activities that shall require more funding support. However, there is still a need to provide substantial and additional financial resources from known and potential sources of funds

4. DepEd Calamba City designed curriculum framework to address the unique needs of the learners in the distance learning particularly in the five key dimensions namely safe operations, well-being and protection, teaching and learning, reaching the marginalized and education financing.

In the study of Oribiana, et.al (2021), pedagogy, technology and material resources are some of the challenges encounters to ensure the continuity of learning (Luz, 2020). To deliver equal opportunities on the identified learning modalities teachers, parents and learners are factors that greatly affect the school learning performance. Thus, Department of Education Secretary Dr. Briones mandate schools to implement capacity building and establish support mechanism to ensure the seamless transition of learning activities into the New Normal format. The objective of the study is to know how parents, learners and teachers will be able to cope up with the new learning set-up. How these respondents embrace the changes and how their experiences affect the delivery and acquisition of learning as well as the implications of the crisis in the respondents' personality as a whole.

Based on the results, the new intervention model, Three-way Teaching and Learning Process in the New Normal, was established. The model integrate process between each participant such observation, communication, instruction, interaction, support and participation. These processes were found to be significant in ensuring the success of the new learning set-up. The corner of the model states the focus interventions such as communication access, professional development, digital collaboration, independent learning, stakeholder engagement and parental education. It is recommended to adopt the intervention model in the Division and School learning continuity plan.

Similar studies show that there is a need to develop policy briefs for curriculum enhancement and effective implementation of distance learning that will cater the needs of the learners. Data reveal that school indicators in access and quality significantly diminished therefore, the present study would like to assess the level of school implementation on the key dimensions of Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan (BE-LCP).

General Objectives of the Study:

The present study aims to measure the level of school implementation on the key dimensions of Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan (BE-LCP) which will be the basis on designing policy brief for distance learning.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

1. What is the mean level of school implementation on the key dimensions of Basic education Learning Continuity Plan in terms of:

1.1 Safe operations;

1.2 Well-being;

1.3 Teaching and Learning;

1.4 Reaching the Marginalized; and

1.5 Education Financing?

2. What is the school level of performance in terms of the following indicators:

2.1 average data of learners;

2.2 drop-out rate;

2.3 retention rate; and

2.4 SBM level of practice?

3. Is there a significant relationship between the level of implementation of the key dimensions and school performance indicators?

4. Based on the findings and recommendation, what policy brief for distance learning can be proposed?

THEORETICAL/CONCEPTUAL BASIS

Adoption of the Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan (BE-LCP) for school year 2020-2021 in light of the covid-19 public health emergency states that the key elements of the learning strategies that shall operationalize the BE-LCP are the streamlining of the K to 12 Curriculum into the Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELCs), and allowing of multiple learning delivery modalities such as distance learning and blended learning, either on top or in place of face-to-face learning delivery modality. To help learners, parents, and teachers implement these learning delivery modalities, Self-Learning Modules (SLMs) shall be made available in print and offline/online digital format, for use this incoming school year. DepEd shall also tap the materials developed by various partners and entities such as SEAMEO INNOTECH, BASA Pilipinas, Knowledge Channel, Frontlearners Inc., and CHED, among many others (DO_s2020_012).

Likewise, the learning outcomes in the form of knowledge, skills, attitudes and values will be assessed, through portfolio / e-portfolio to include written works, and performances (and products), whether hardcopy, softcopy or a combination of these, and through summative tests as conditions allow. The administration of national examinations shall continue amidst COVID-19.

Distance education itself can be seen as following a pragmatic paradigm because distance education environments provide learners with the ability to learn from any location without needing to visit a brick-and-mortar institution. Learners often like the convenience offered by accessing learning at any time of the day instead of at a scheduled time (Cheng, et.al, 2021)

Dogan (2021) mentioned that in the perspective of pragmatism, theories should be judged by the consequences instead of the origins or relations to antecedent data and theories are instruments to cope with reality and solve problems. In addition, American pragmatists disdain intellectual tendencies. Pragmatism might lead into various schools of thought and ideas because it has no dogma.

Pragmatism is a school of thought that focuses on action, practice, and the idea of the “practical”. According to William James (1907), pragmatism is based on empiricism, but the empiricism is of a radical kind. Pragmatists consider theories as instruments rather than “answers to enigmas, in which we can rest” (James, 1907, p. 26). As James (1907) explained,

Pragmatism unstiffens all our theories, limbers them up and sets each one at work. Being nothing essentially new, it harmonizes with many ancient philosophic tendencies. It agrees with nominalism for instance, in always appealing to particulars; with utilitarianism in emphasizing practical aspects; with positivism in its disdain for verbal solutions, useless questions, and metaphysical abstractions. (p. 26)

2. METHODOLOGY

1. TYPES

The present study will utilize data collection, measurement and analysis. Specifically, descriptive survey and correlational designs will be used since it aims to assess the level of school implementation on the key dimensions and its relation to school performance and indicators.

2. SAMPLING POPULATION

Cluster	School	Enrollment (July 15, 2020)	No. of Teachers	Total number of Respondents		
				Parents	Learners	Teacher
Cluster 1	School A	1866	48	60	60	27
Cluster 2	School B	3824	130	124	124	73
Cluster 3	School C	593	20	20	20	11
Cluster 4	School D	902	24	30	30	13
Cluster 5	School E	1133	33	38	38	18
Cluster 6	School F	1040	31	34	34	17
Cluster 7	School G	1498	41	48	48	23
Cluster 8	School H	1125	25	36	36	14
Cluster 9	School I	295	7	10	10	4
Total		12,007	359	400	400	200

The sampling population is composed of nine schools in the Division of Calamba City representing small, medium, large, and mega large school.

3. SAMPLING METHOD

Stratified random sampling technique will be employed since the researchers want to highlight a specific subgroup within the population. This technique is useful in such researches because it ensures the presence of the key subgroup within the sample. The respondents of the study will be selected teachers, parents and learners from the following schools in the Division of Calamba City

4. TREATMENT/ANALYSIS

Mean and average analysis and Pearson correlation coefficient formula will be used to analyze the data gathered. The Pearson correlation coefficient (r) is used to denote the linear relationship between two variables x and y whereby the Pearson value must be between -1 and $+1$. If Pearson's r is negative, then the relationship is also negative, and if it is positive, the relationship is positive.

3. CONCLUSION

Based on the findings, the following conclusions are made:

The mean and average analysis of the level of school implementation on the key dimensions of basic education learning continuity plan (BE-LCP): A Basis on Designing Policy Brief for Distance Learning in the Division of Calamba City. The Mean of Distance learning or using self-learning modules is shown to be feasible alternative in lieu of designing policy brief in relation to the school implementation on the key dimension of BE-LCP.

The researchers seek out evidence that provides the proposed correlation between the two variables such as parents and teachers which is used as interest. It is sensible to bring that there is no quantifiable difference between a distance learning and the implementation of BE-LCP in terms of quality. Provided the right teacher and learners are put together, these learners receive just as in distance education / online as others do on a regular school.

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